

Research Article

Utilization of Bird Species in Traditional Medicine in Selected Markets in Ibadan
Metropolis

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Abstract

This study was carried out to identify bird species that are used in medicine. One hundred and twenty-two (122) questionnaires were administered and 94 were collected and used to assess information in the use of bird species for traditional medicine. The result showed the importance of bird species in traditional medicine with regards to ailments treated. According to the respondents, (95% say epilepsy can be treated with a preparation of vulture intestines, also rheumatism with the blood of owl (according to 92% of the respondent), likewise tuberculosis with duck. Human belief in relation to bird species was documented e.g., persistent taboos on some birds and the assumption that some birds are sacred, according to 89% of the respondents and seasonal variation in availability of bird species in the market was discovered i.e. vulture owl wet season (according to 100% of the traders). Questionnaires were distributed among bird species trader/traditional medical practitioners snowball sampling. Recommendations were made for establishing scientific evidence to know the efficacy of bird species used for the treatment of some ailments and also the encouragement and improvement of traditional medicine through proper funding and policy making by the Government.

Keywords: Utilization, Market, Metropolis, Bird species, Traditional

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Introduction

Among non-scientist, birds are the favored of all animals, largely because they are the obvious, because of their colors and their songs. They have also received more than their fair share of attention from scientists and result of this is that it is likely that new species will be discovered in the future. Another consequence of this attention is that the classification of birds has reached a stable form. In this classification, 27 orders of living birds are enumerated, with two more for recently extinct moas of New Zealand and elephant birds of Madagascar (Padian, 2000). This is a higher proportion of orders for a single class of animals than in any other area of the animal kingdom.

Side-by-side with this, it has to be recognized that there are few, if any, other major groups of animals so poorly represented by fossils, are birds. Fortunately, there are remarkably complete fossils of earliest known bird, the Archaeopteryx, the so-called lizard - bird, that indicate very clearly are an evolution of birds from reptilian ancestors. This paucity of fossils is probably to be correlated with the habits, so that, as has often been said by a paleontologist, "birds do not make good fossils". The situation is similar to bats, but not for the pterodactyls or flying reptiles. This absence of all but a scattered fossil is the more remarkable when it is recalled that birds have certainly been in existence for about 180 million years (Blunt, 1994).

The class Aves used to be divided into two main divisions: the Ratitate and carinatae, the first including the flightless, running birds, such as Ostrich, emu, cassowary, rhea and kiwi, the second including all the rest. Today, the surviving ratites are being assigned to four separate orders, the struthioniformes (ostriches), Rheiformes (rheas), cassuariiformes (emus, cassowaries) and Apterygiformes (kiwis) on the assumption that these birds are not necessarily related but look alike as a result of convergent evolution (Padian, 2000). Birds are bipedal, warm-blooded animals that lay eggs. There are around 10,000 living species, making them the most numerous tetrapod vertebrates. They inhabit ecosystems across the globe, from the Arctic to the Antarctic. Birds ranges in sizes from the 5cm (2 in) Bee Hummingbird to the 2.7m (9ft) Ostrich (Zhou, 2004).

Modern birds are characterized by feathers, a beak with no teeth, the laying of hard-shelled eggs, a high metabolic rate, a four-chambered heart and a lightweight but strong skeleton. All birds have forelimbs modified as wings and most can fly, with some exceptions, including ratites, penguins, and numbers of diverse endemic island species. Birds also have unique digestive and respiratory systems that are highly adapted for flight (Clarke, 2004).

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Many species undertake long distance annual migrations and many more perform shorter irregular monuments. Birds are social; they communicate using visual signals and through calls and songs, and participate in social behaviors including co-operative breeding and hunting, flocking and mobbing of predators. The vast majority of bird species are socially monogamous, usually for one breeding season at a time, sometimes for years, but rarely for life. Other species have breeding systems that are polygynous ("many males"). Eggs are usually laid in a nest and incubated by the parents. Most birds have an extended period of parental care after hatching (Gill, 2006).

Now that there is a growing recognition with regards to the contribution of bird species in traditional medicine is a step towards healthcare developments, it is proper for such initiative to be given recognition and support in order to be accomplished, articulated programmes on medical, importance of bird species, researches and initiatives as in this study is directed at the utilization of bird species in traditional medicine. The government, private sectors, non- governmental organizations (NGOs) relating to wildlife, research institutes and colleges need to be aware that studies and researches that will promote the full and judicious utilization of bird species for various beneficial purposes other than consumption is needed to be conducted.

Materials and methods

Description of the Study Area

Ibadan is the capital city of Oyo State, Nigeria and is located-lately on longitude 3°54° East of Greenwich Meridian and latitude North of the equator at a distance of about 145km Northeast of Lagos. It has a total land area of 130km and is 750m above sea level.

Climate

Ibadan has the characteristic of West African Monsoon climate marked by a distinct seasonal shift in the wind pattern (Oguntoyinbo, 1987). The rainy season begins around March and ends around October under the influence of the moist maritime southeast monsoon wind which blows inland from the Atlantic Ocean. The dry season starts around November and ends around February with the dry dust laden wind blowing from the Sahara desert. The means the total minimum temperature is 22°C while the mean total maximum temperature is 31.5°C. The mean total annual rainfall is 1412.4mm. The mean total relative humidity is 79.96% (Department of Meteorological Science, Federal Ministry of Civil Aviation Zonal Office Ibadan, 1989).

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Topography and drainage

There are three major land forms in Ibadan and these are hills, plains and valleys. The most striking features are the hills which make up only about 5% of the total area and run approximately northeast direction. The hills such as Mapo, Mokola and Aremo hills contain the highest peaks in the central pan of the city. They have an elevation ranging between 160m and 275m above sea level.

The plains constitute 80% of the total area eventually covers hill bases and entrenched valley bottom with a general elevation ranging between 180m and 210m above sea level. Ibadan is drained by two major rivers: River Ogunpa and River Ona. River Ogunpa drains the eastern part while River Ona drains the western part while River Ona drains the western part. Tributaries of these rivers included Rivers Alapata, Ogbere, Kudeti, Alalubosa, Osun and Yemoja.

Soil and vegetation

The soils of Ibadan were formed from rocks of pre-Cambian basement, especially of granite gneisses, Quartz-schist, biotic gneisses and schist (Andy, 1992). They were formed under moist semi-deciduous forest cover and belong to the ferruginous tropical soils. The quartzite ridges have good vegetation, especially the undisturbed area. This may be as a result of the existence of thick soils and also because of the generally steep slopes limiting the intensity humid interference.

Population of the Study

The population of this study is made up of those who trade in bird species and other bird parts/products in Ibadan. One hundred and twenty two (122) Questionnaires were administered to 122 traders who deal on wildlife for traditional medicinal preparations in selected markets, while 97 Questionnaires were retrieved.

Sampling Technique

Three markets were purposively sampled for their involvement in bird species trade 79.5% of the population involved in the activity was sampled. The markets sampled were - Bode, Oranyan and Oje. The snowball sampling technique was used to elicit responses from respondents.

Method of Data Collection

This research work employed personal interview and structured questionnaire. Data were collected on visits to existing markets within Ibadan metropolis (Oje, Oranyan, and Bode markets).

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The questionnaire sought information on the folio wings:

- i. Personal bio-data
- ii. Part(s) of bird species used in traditional medicine
- iii. Human belief in relation to birds.
- iv. Seasonal variation in availability of bird species.

Method of Data Analysis

All data collected were subjected to appropriate statistical tools which include descriptive statistic such as frequency count, line graphs and percentage.

Results and Discussions

Table 1 reveals the distribution of respondents based on their gender. The males that are involved in selling of bird species makes a total of 25% while female are 75%. From the result, it shows that female are mostly engaged in bird species trading, it demands an interest in men's involvement in the trade so as to boost the business.

Table 1: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	24
Female	73	73
Total	97	100

Table 2: Age range of respondents

Age distribution (years)	Frequency	Percentage
Below 20	-	-
21 - 30	9	9.3
31-40	18	18.6
41-50	51	52.6
>50	19	19.5
Total	97	100

Table 2 reveals the distribution of respondents based on their age range. There is no trader below the age of 20 while 9.3% falls within the age of 21 - 30, however the greatest percentage (52.6%) are within 41-50 years. This is in accordance with Durojaiye (2006) which affirms that the majority (80%) of pie who trades in animal parts for

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traditional medicine is between the ages of 40 - 60. The result indicates that bird species business demand great deal of awareness to the youth.

Table 3: Educational Level.

Education qualification	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	55	56.7
Primary education	26	26.8
Secondary education	165	16.5
Tertiary education	-	-
Total	97	100

Table 3 indicates the education status of various bird species traders i.e. 55.7% of the respondents are those with no formal educational qualification while 26.8% and 16.5% have primary and secondary educational background respectively. The implications of this is that most of the respondents are those with no or low educational level due to the fact that the acquisition of practical knowledge of the trade is by family/tradition.

Table 4: Religion of the respondents.

Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Islam	11	11.6
Christianity	9	9.3
Traditional	77	79.4
Islam	11	11.6
Total	97	100

Table 4 reveals that 11.6% and 9.3% of the respondents are Muslims and Christians respectively, which 79.4% are traditionalist, which shows that the trade is practiced mostly by the traditionalist. It requires involvement of other religion members since it is a lifesaving occupation.

Table 5: Practical knowledge

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Family tradition	94	96.9
Acquired skill	3	3.1
Total	97	100

Table 6: Level of involvement

Mode	Frequency	Percentage
Full time	97	100
Part time	-	-
Others	-	-
Total	97	100

Table 5 reveals that 94% of the respondents inherited the trade as family tradition while only 3% have acquired skills. The response of the respondents shows that the trade is a more or less family inherited trade than a learned skill.

Table 6 shows that all the respondents are fully involved in trade, which 100% of the respondents are in full time venture. This is due to the educational level of the traders (i.e. 55.7%) of the respondents are with no formal education as the trade can be practiced alongside other business to increase income.

Table 7: List of bird species used in traditional medicine within the study area

S/no	Local name	Common name	Zoological name
1.	Igunugun	Vulture	<i>Gyps africanus</i>
2.	Owiwi	Owl	<i>Tyto alba</i>
3.	Lekeleke	Cattle Egret	<i>Ardeola ibis</i>
4.	Asa	Eagle	<i>Polemaetus bellicosus</i>
5.	Odidere	Long tail dove	<i>Oena capensis</i>
6.	Elulu	Senegal conceal	<i>Centropus Senegalensis</i>
7.	Kowee	Levaillant coucou	<i>Clamator levaillantii</i>
8.	Ogbigbi-nta	Dogra cheel	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>
9.	Eyele	Pigeon	<i>Columbia spp</i>
10.	Adaba	Red eyed turtle dove	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>
11.	Ofeere	Hens low sparrow	<i>Ammodramus henslowii</i>
12.	Ega	Village weaver	<i>Ploceus cuculletus</i>
13.	Ayekooto	Parrot	<i>Ara ararauna</i>
14.	Akoko	Woodpecker	<i>Mesopiscos spp</i>
15.	Kanakana	Lizard Buzzard	<i>Kaupifalcon monogrammicus</i>
16.	Opeere/Tintin	Bronze Mannikin	<i>Lonclura bicolor</i>
17.	Akalamagbo	Layyard parakee	<i>Calthrope blyth</i>
18.	Alapanadede	Mosque swallow	<i>Hirundo senegalensis</i>
19.	Pepeiye	Duck	<i>Cygnus atratus</i>
20.	Awo/Etu	Guinea fowl	<i>Nunida meleageris</i>
21.	Eye omi	King fisher	<i>Halcyon spp</i>

Table 8: Seasonal variations in availability birds

Birds	Season	Frequency	Percentage
Vulture	Wet season	97	100
Owl	Wet season	97	100

Table 8 shows that only vulture and owl are the bird species that affected by the seasonal variation (according to the respondent i.e. 100%) both species are affected by rainfall as it will not allow them to take off flight easily. The implication is that, at these periods they will move to high trees/mountain where they can take off flight easily which make them very difficult to capture.

Table 9: List of bird regarded as sacred/taboo.

Common name	Reasons	Consequences	% of the respondent that agree	% of the respondent that disagree
Vulture	Forbid to be consume anyone	Small pox (Igbona) will attack whoever eats it.	87	10
Cattle Egret	It must not be killed by anyone.	It's white body turns black when killed and that this mean a curse on whoever eat it	87	10
Senegal concol	It's responsible for rainfall/precipitation	There is a curse on whoever kills it because it will affect rainfall in the area.	87	10
Levaillant coucou	If it is seen on the roof of any house making sound, though the consequences depend on the type of sound that the bird made.	It reveals death when sighted on house top roof making some stirringly sound or it make a bad sign.	87	10
Layyard parakee	It must not be killed and eaten by anyone	If it is accidentally killed it must not be made known to people and sacrifices must be made to avert curses that can befall the killer.	87	10

Due to the belief of the people, 87% of the respondents agree that there are some bird species that are regarded as sacred. Strong belief has been attached to it and people still respect it, i.e. the bird species. Some of this bird species and the reason why they are regarded as sacred as well as their consequences are listed in Table 9.

Table 10: Birds/birds part used in traditional medicine.

Conditions birds	Birds utilized	Parts of the birds	Frequency	Percentage	Total
Epilepsy	Vulture	Intestines	93	95	97
Rheumatism	Owl	Blood	90	92	97
Chronic headache	Eagle	Head	57	58	97
Eye worms	Pigeon	Feathers	92	94	97
High blood pressure	Dove	Heart	51	52	97
Diabetes	Hawk	Gizzard	49	50	97
Measles/Asthma	Village weaver	Head + heart	61	62	97
Chicken/small pox	Vulture	Blood + Intestine	53	54	97
Blood cure	Owl	Intestine + Blood	91	93	97
Tuberculosis	Duck	Whole body	63	64	97

Table 10 reveals the birds/bird parts that are used in traditional medicine with the ailment treated according to the respondents.

Conclusion

From the study, it is concluded that the existence of birds cannot be over emphasized as results have shown that some bird parts such as that of pigeon, owl etc have been found out to be very important in curing some specified types of ailments e.g. epilepsy, rheumatism, asthma etc. and the presence of birds in the locality is based on the season of which such birds are prominent (seasonal variation). There are still persistent taboos on some birds and the assumption that some birds are sacred which enhanced the availability of birds for usage preventing such birds from extinction.

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This result showed that bird species trade/business is mostly practiced by those in their prime age and if given needed attention and involvement of youths would grow and reduced the growing unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested.

- i. Efforts must be geared in Nigeria towards establishing scientific evidence for the efficacy claimed for bird species for treatments of some ailments with a view to incorporating the potent ones into the health care system of the country so that drug production will be enhanced. Such effort will eventually reduce the total dependence on imported drugs and lead to great self-reliance on our pharmaceutical services.
- ii. Government through funding and policy should make research in traditional medicine an interesting one to interested individuals. This may be achieved given out grants on new development in traditional medicine.
- iii. Since birds contribute to the natural ecosystem, human health and nutrition therefore bush burning, unregulated shooting/hunting of birds species should be discouraged.
- iv. The extension agents from government parastatals should be able to disseminate the latest information on bird species uses to increase the knowledge of bird species traders.
- v. There should be publications on bird species utilization in traditional medicine for public awareness.

References

Andy E. and Jordi S. (1992). Handbook of Birds of the World, volume 1: Ostrich to Ducks. Barcelona: Lynx Edicions.

Blunt, W., Raphael, S. (1994). The Illustrated Herbal. Thomas and Hudson Inc., New York, pp 190.

Clarke, J. A. (September 2004) "Morphology, Phylogenetic Taxonomy, and Systematics of Ichthyornis and Apatornis (Avialae "Ornithurae"). *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* Pp. 286.

Gill, F. (2006). Birds of the World: Recommended English Names. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Oguntoyinbo, J.S. (1987). Climatic characteristics in Ibadan region edited by Filani of Geography Department, University of Ibadan P.J. 49.

Padian, K. (2000). "Bird Origins", in Philip J. Currie & Kevin Padian (eds.): Encyclopedia of Dinosaurs. San Diego: Academic Press, pp 41-96.

Zhou, Z. (2004). "The Origin and Early Evolution of Birds: Discoveries, Disputes and Perspectives from Fossil Evidence". Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press. Pp 91.